

Research Article

Determination of Antioxidant Activity of Honey and *Cordyceps* Mixtures

Theodor-Ioan Badea and Emanuel Vamanu*

Faculty of Biotechnology, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Bucharest, Romania

Abstract

The paper aims to determine the antioxidant potential of mixtures of acacia honey with the medicinal *Cordyceps sinensis* fungus. The main objective was to evaluate the synergistic effect between the bioactive compounds of the two components by determining the antioxidant potential both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. The *in vitro* antioxidant power of the mixtures increased with increasing mycelium concentration (0.1%, 0.2%, 0.5%) compared to the control represented by plain honey, indicating a positive correlation between mycelium content and antioxidant capacity. *In vivo* tests, performed by analyzing the viability of *Saccharomyces boulardii* yeast in the presence of hydrogen peroxide, confirmed the more pronounced protective effect of the mixtures, especially for the 0.5% *C. sinensis* concentration. The results suggest a significant synergistic effect between acacia honey and *C. sinensis*, with potential applications in the development of natural products with superior antioxidant and therapeutic properties.

Keywords: Acacia Honey; Peroxide; *S. Boulardii*; Viability/Mortality

Introduction

The entomopathogenic fungus *Cordyceps sinensis*, renamed *Ophiocordyceps sinensis* [1] is one of the best-known ingredients used in traditional medicine in China [2]. *C. sinensis* is a fungus that parasitizes *Hepialus armoricanus* moth larvae [3].

C. sinensis contains numerous bioactive constituents (polysaccharides, cordycepin, cordycepic acid, adenosine and ergosterol). The polysaccharides contained in *C. sinensis* have antioxidant, immunomodulatory, and anti-fibrotic activities [4], nucleosides can have

*Corresponding author: Emanuel Vamanu, Faculty of Biotechnology, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine, Bucharest, Romania, Tel: +40 742218240; E-mail: emmanuel.vamanu@bth.usamv.ro

Citation: Badea T-I, Vamanu E (2026) Determination of Antioxidant Activity of Honey and Cordyceps Mixtures. HSOA J Altern Complement Integr Med 12: 703.

Received: April 24, 2026; **Accepted:** May 07, 2026; **Published:** May 14, 2026

Copyright: © 2026 Badea T-I, et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

positive effects on macrophages [5] and cordycepin has antitumor and immunoregulatory effects [6]. Hydroalcoholic extracts from cultivated *C. sinensis* cultures exhibited complex activities (antioxidant and anti-lipid peroxidation and inhibited cholesterol ester accumulation in macrophages by suppressing LDL oxidation) [7]. Studies have shown that the mycelia of cultivated mushrooms and natural mushrooms had equally strong antioxidant activity [8].

Acacia honey contains numerous bioactive compounds (vitamins, phenols, flavonoids, fatty acids), is highly nutritious, has strong antioxidant properties as well as a high immunomodulatory potential, and can be considered a potential candidate for both the prevention of cancer as well as its treatment [9].

The aim of this study is to establish the functional value of mixtures of acacia honey and *C. sinensis* mycelium by characterizing them *in vitro* and *in vivo*.

Materials and Methods

The subject of this analysis was acacia honey as well as its mixtures with increasing concentrations of *Cordyceps* (0.1%, 0.2% and 0.5%).

The honey was obtained from the online store stupinagrama.ro and the *Cordyceps sinensis* powder was purchased from the online store natur.ro.

In vitro determination of total phenolic content was carried out with the use of the Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, while flavonoid content was determined with the quercetin method.

In vitro antioxidant activity was determined using the ABTS method. The ABTS test allows the evaluation of total antioxidant activity [10].

All determinations were performed in triplicate.

Determination of phenols was performed with 0.25 mL of aqueous extract mixed with 1 mL 1 M sodium carbonate and 1.25 mL Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. After 15 min, optical density was measured at 765 nm (1 cm cuvette) against a blank. Results were expressed as μg gallic acid/g honey [11].

Determination of flavonoids was performed using the visible-range method, which is based on complexation of flavonoids with aluminum chloride (AlCl_3) in the presence of sodium acetate. 0.1 mL 10% AlCl_3 was added to 0.5 mL sample or standard, followed by 0.1 mL 1 M CH_3COONa and 2.8 mL distilled water. After vigorous mixing and 10 min incubation at room temperature, absorbance was read at 415 nm against a blank (AlCl_3 replaced by water). Quercetin 100 μM was used as standard [12].

In vivo antioxidant activity was determined with the use of a culture of *S. boulardii*. A mixture of 10% dilution (0.1 mL), yeast solution (0.1 mL), and was treated with 0.2 mL of hydrogen peroxide in different concentrations (0, 0.5%, 1%, 2%, 3%). The control consisted of *S.*

boulardii treated with 0.9% NaCl. The mixtures were incubated for 1 hour at 37°C, after which the number of viable cells and the number of dead cells were read on a Thoma slide. The cells were stained with methylene blue.

The critical exposure point of *S. boulardii* yeast to hydrogen peroxide (determined by the intersection of the viability curve with the mortality curve) was also determined.

To validate the results, 2-way ANOVA statistical analysis was applied for $p < 0.05$ and Post hoc Tukey, using a Python program.

Results

Determination of polyphenols and flavonoids in vitro

The total content of polyphenols and flavonoids in the test mixtures increased with the concentration of mycelium. In particular, the 0.5% concentration showed the highest growth in both phenols and flavonoids (Figures 1 & 2).

Figure 1: Determination of the polyphenol content of acacia honey with *Cordyceps* in different concentrations.

Figure 2: Determination of the flavonoid content of acacia honey with *Cordyceps* in different concentrations.

Determination of antioxidant activity in vitro

Both acacia honey [13] and *Cordyceps* [14] exhibit antioxidant activity.

The antioxidant power of acacia honey increased with the addition of *Cordyceps* extract, indicating the synergistic effect of the two components and a positive correlation between antioxidant activity and mycelium concentration in honey and mushroom preparations (Figure 3). Compared to the control (acacia honey), the antioxidant activity of the preparations containing the mushroom increased 1.1307 times for *Cordyceps* 0.1%, 1.3154 times for *Cordyceps* 0.2%, and 1.4170 times for *Cordyceps* 0.5% (Table 1).

Polysaccharides in *C. sinensis* are the main bioactive components, possessing antioxidant, liver-protective and anti-aging activity. Exopolysaccharides from cultivated *Cordyceps sinensis* possess ABTS and hydroxyl scavenging capacities [15,16]. *In vitro* assessments of antioxidant activity showed that aqueous extracts from cultivated samples had a stronger radical scavenging power as well as showing a higher reducing power [17].

Figure 3: Determination of the antioxidant potential of acacia honey with *Cordyceps* in different concentrations.

Sample	Antioxidant activity (%)	Control Ratio
Control (Acacia Honey)	51.0825 ± 3.3320	-
Acacia + <i>Cordyceps</i> 0.1%	57.7608 ± 1.9255	1.1307
Acacia + <i>Cordyceps</i> 0.2%	67.1941 ± 2.0838	1.3154
Acacia + <i>Cordyceps</i> 0.5%	72.3867 ± 0.6436	1.4170

Table 1: Antioxidant potential of acacia honey + *Cordyceps* (0.1%; 0.2%; 0.5%) compared to the control (acacia honey).

A higher total phenolic content and greater reducing activity were found in honey mixed with *Coriolus versicolor*. This indicates the mushroom has a significant quantity of antioxidants [18]. Also, supplementing acacia honey with 0.5% reishi mushroom extract (*Ganoderma lucidum*) significantly increased the total polyphenol content,

antioxidant activity, and free radical scavenging power, with a statistically significant improvement in the prebiotic index for the honey-mushroom mixture compared to pure acacia honey [19].

Determination of antioxidant activity *in vivo*. Viability and mortality of *S. boulardii* in the presence of hydrogen peroxide

In the case of the control (*S. boulardii* treated with 0.9% NaCl), the viability of *S. boulardii* at a peroxide concentration of 3% was 31.336%. The viability of *S. boulardii* decreased from 96.247% to 89.296% at a concentration of 0.5% peroxide, after which it decreased slightly at 1% peroxide. The viability of the yeast decreased continuously to 31.336% (at a peroxide concentration of 3%), with the critical point of exposure to peroxide at 2.722% (approx.), when a viability of 50% was recorded. At 3% peroxide, mortality was 70%. In the case of the acacia honey sample without *Cordyceps*, the *S. boulardii* viability curve was similar, with a critical exposure point of 2.77% peroxide and 50% viability. Yeast viability decreased to 35.37% at 3% peroxide; at this peroxide concentration, mortality was 64.621% (Figures 4 & 5).

Figure 4: Viability (%) and mortality (%) of *S. boulardii* treated with peroxide and 0.9% NaCl.

Figure 5: Viability (%) and mortality (%) of *S. boulardii* treated with peroxide and acacia honey.

In the three samples of acacia honey + *Cordyceps*, yeast viability increased with increasing *Cordyceps* concentration. Initially, the viability of *S. boulardii* decreased at 0.5% peroxide and stagnated at 1% peroxide, at concentrations of 0.1% and 0.2% *Cordyceps*; followed by a continuous decrease in viability to 43.513% and 44.812%, respectively, at the maximum peroxide concentration of 3%. Mortality at 3% peroxide was 56.486% with 0.1% *Cordyceps* and 55.187% at

0.2% *Cordyceps*. The critical exposure point was 2.876% peroxide with 0.1% *Cordyceps* and 2.894% at 0.2% *Cordyceps*. In the acacia honey + 0.5% *Cordyceps* sample, the viability of *S. boulardii* decreased continuously from 97.272% correlated with the increase in peroxide concentration to 49.308% at 3% peroxide concentration, when the critical exposure point was also recorded. Viability and mortality were 50% (Figures 6-8).

Figure 6: Viability (%) and mortality (%) of *S. boulardii* treated with peroxide and acacia honey mixed with 0.1% *Cordyceps*.

Figure 7: Viability (%) and mortality (%) of *S. boulardii* treated with peroxide and acacia honey mixed with 0.2% *Cordyceps*.

The viability of *S. boulardii* decreased with increasing peroxide concentration, but in the presence of 3% peroxide, the effect of *Cordyceps* was visible at all three concentrations.

Figure 8: Viability (%) and mortality (%) of *S. boulardii* treated with peroxide and acacia honey mixed with 0.5% *Cordyceps*.

Thus, the honey + *Cordyceps* 0.5% sample showed the highest yeast viability (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Influence of *Cordyceps* in honey on the viability of *S. boulardii* (%) treated with peroxide.

Critical point of *S. boulardii* cultures in the presence of peroxide

The critical point of *S. Boulardii* cultures treated with hydrogen peroxide increased as the *Cordyceps* concentration increased (Figure 10). The lowest critical point was recorded in the control, followed by acacia honey, and the highest critical point was in acacia honey + *Cordyceps* 0.5%. In this case, the critical point increased by 2.99 compared to the control, while in honey + *Cordyceps* 0.1% and 0.2% it was higher by 2.876 and 2.894 times, respectively (Table 2).

Figure 10: Critical point of *S. boulardii* cultures in the presence of peroxide.

Statistical analysis of *S. boulardii* viability and mortality

According to the results obtained (Tables 3 & 4) there is a statistically significant difference between the effects of different *Cordyceps* concentrations on *S. boulardii* viability/mortality.

Sample	Critical Point (%)	Control Ratio
Control	2.72	-
Acacia Honey	2.77	1.018
Acacia + <i>Cordyceps</i> 0.1%	2.876	1.057
Acacia + <i>Cordyceps</i> 0.2%	2.894	1.063
Acacia + <i>Cordyceps</i> 0.5%	2.990	1.099

Table 2: The critical point of *S. Boulardii* cultures under the influence of increasing concentrations of *Cordyceps*.

	df	sum_sq	F	PR(>F)	p_value	Significance (p<0.05)
Composition	4	453.08	21.92	1.700791e-10	p < .01	Significant
Peroxide Concentration	4	30354.42	1468.6	3.711488e-51	p < .01	Significant
Composition* Concentration	16	395.51	4.78	9.955446e-06	p < .01	Significant
Residual	50	258.36				

Table 3: 2 way ANOVA for *S. boulardii* viability.

	df	sum_sq	F	PR(>F)	p_value	Significance (p<0.05)
Composition	4	453.08	21.92	1.700791e-10	p < .01	Significant
Peroxide Concentration	4	30354.42	1468.6	3.711488e-51	p < .01	Significant
Composition* Concentration	16	395.51	4.78	9.955446e-06	p < .01	Significant
Residual	50	258.36				

Table 4: 2 way ANOVA for *S. boulardii* mortality.

Post hoc Tuckey analysis (Table 5) reveals an important difference between acacia honey and its blend with 0.1% *Cordyceps*, suggesting only a small amount of the mushroom is needed to achieve significant benefits.

Group 1	Group 2	Meandiff	p-adj	Lower	Upper	Reject
Control	Acacia	4.0426	0.8742	-3.139	11.2241	False
Acacia	Acacia+C0.1%	-8.1352	0.0117	-15.3167	-0.9537	True
Acacia+C0.1%	Acacia+C0.2%	1.299	1.0	-5.8826	8.4805	False
Acacia+C0.2%	Acacia+C0.5%	4.4959	0.7396	-2.6857	11.6774	False

Table 5: Post hoc Tuckey for *S. boulardii* viability in 3% Peroxide.

Discussion

Both acacia honey and its mixture with *Cordyceps sinensis* had antioxidant activity.

The higher viability of *S. boulardii* recorded in acacia honey samples with *Cordyceps sinensis* mycelium indicated that the fungus has significant antioxidant activity.

The experiments showed that there is a positive correlation between antioxidant activity and the concentration of *Cordyceps sinensis* in honey and mushroom preparations.

The critical point of exposure of *S. boulardii* yeast to hydrogen peroxide (determined by the intersection of the viability and mortality curves) was present in all samples, including the control. As the peroxide concentration increased, the viability of the yeast decreased and the mortality values increased. The critical exposure point recorded increasing values as the concentration of *C. sinensis* increased in the acacia honey samples with mycelium.

References

- Lo HC, Hsieh C, Lin FY, Hsu TH (2013) A Systematic Review of the Mysterious Caterpillar Fungus *Ophiocordyceps sinensis* in Dong-ChongXia-Cao (Dong Chong Xia Cao) and Related Bioactive Ingredients. *J Tradit Complement Med* 3: 16-32.
- Dong CH, Yao YJ (2008) In vitro evaluation of antioxidant activities of aqueous extracts from natural and cultured mycelia of *Cordyceps sinensis*. *Lebensm Wiss Technol* 41: 669-677.
- Jing-Kun Yan, Wen-Qiang Wang, Jian-Yong Wu (2014) Recent advances in *Cordyceps sinensis* polysaccharides: Mycelial fermentation, isolation, structure, and bioactivities: A review. *Journal of Functional Foods* 6: 33-47.
- Yao Y, Wu M, Huang Y, Li C, Pan X, et al. (2017) Appropriately raising fermentation temperature beneficial to the increase of antioxidant activity and gallic acid content in *Eurotium cristatum*-fermented loose tea. *LWT - Food Science and Technology* 82: 248-254.
- Yu L, Zhao J, Zhu Q, Li SP (2007) Macrophage biospecific extraction and high performance liquid chromatography for hypothesis of immunological active components in *Cordyceps sinensis*. *Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biomedical Analysis* 44: 439-443.
- Jeong JW, Jin CY, Park C, Hong SH, Kim GY, et al. (2011) Induction of apoptosis by cordycepin via reactive oxygen species generation in human leukemia cells. *ELSEVIER BV* 25: 817.
- Yamaguchi Y, Kagota S, Nakamura K, Shinozuka K, Kunitomo M (2000) Antioxidant activity of the extracts from fruiting bodies of cultured *Cordyceps sinensis*. *Phytother Res* 14: 647-649.
- Li SP, Li P, Dong TT, Tsim KW (2001) Anti-oxidation activity of different types of natural *Cordyceps sinensis* and cultured *Cordyceps* mycelia. *Phytomedicine* 8: 207-212.
- Muhammad A, Odunola OA, Ibrahim MA, Sallau AB, Erukainure OL, et al. (2016) Potential biological activity of acacia honey. *Front Biosci (Elite Ed)* 8: 351-357.
- Floegel A, Kim D-O, Chung S-J, Koo SI, Chun OK (2011) Comparison of ABTS/DPPH Assays to Measure Antioxidant Capacity in Popular Antioxidant-Rich US Foods. *Journal of Food Composition and Analysis* 24: 1043-1048.
- Singleton VL, Joseph A, Rossi JR (1965) Colorant of total phenolics with phosphomolibdy phosphotungstic acid reagent. *Am J Enol Vitic* 16: 144.
- Pekal A, Pyrzynska K (2014) Evaluation of Aluminium Complexation Reaction for Flavonoid Content Assay. *Food Anal Methods* 7: 1776-1782.
- Krpan M, Marković K, Šarić G, Skoko B, Hruškar M, et al. (2009) Antioxidant Activities and Total Phenolics of Acacia Honey. *Czech J Food Sci* 27: 245-247.
- Zhu YY, Wu MMH, Zhao ZC, Gu FT, Huang LX, et al. (2025) An Antioxidative Exopolysaccharide-Protein Complex of *Cordyceps Cs-HK1* Fungus and Its Epithelial Barrier-Protective Effects in Caco-2 Cell Culture. *Antioxidants* 14: 1501.
- Nguyen QV, Vu TT, Tran MT, Thi PTH, Thu H, et al. (2021) Antioxidant Activity and Hepatoprotective Effect of Exopolysaccharides From Cultivated *Ophiocordyceps Sinensis* Against CCl4-Induced Liver Damages. *Natural Product Communications* 16.
- He M, Tang CY, Wang T, Xiao MJ, Li YL, et al. (2024) Analysis of Metabolic Profiles and Antioxidant Activity of Chinese *Cordyceps*, *Ophiocordyceps sinensis*, and *Paecilomyces hepiali* Based on Untargeted Metabolomics. *Biology* 13: 683.
- Wang J, Kan L, Nie S, Chen H, Cui SW, et al. (2015) A comparison of chemical composition, bioactive components and antioxidant activity of natural and cultured *Cordyceps sinensis*. *LWT - Food Science and Technology* 63: 2-7.
- Pantovic J, Maskovic P, Niksic M, Nikicevic N (2014) The antioxidant activity of honey and honey with added mushroom *Coriolus versicolor*. *Fifth International Scientific Agricultural Symposium, Agrosym 2014*: 534-537.
- Kiss A, Mirmazloum I, Naár Z, Némédi E (2019) Supplementation of Lingzhi or Reishi Medicinal Mushroom, *Ganoderma lucidum* (Agaricomycetes) Extract Enhanced the Medicinal Values and Prebiotic Index of Hungarian Acacia Honey. *Int J Med Mushrooms* 21: 1167-1179.

- Advances In Industrial Biotechnology | ISSN: 2639-5665
- Advances In Microbiology Research | ISSN: 2689-694X
- Archives Of Surgery And Surgical Education | ISSN: 2689-3126
- Archives Of Urology
- Archives Of Zoological Studies | ISSN: 2640-7779
- Current Trends Medical And Biological Engineering
- International Journal Of Case Reports And Therapeutic Studies | ISSN: 2689-310X
- Journal Of Addiction & Addictive Disorders | ISSN: 2578-7276
- Journal Of Agronomy & Agricultural Science | ISSN: 2689-8292
- Journal Of AIDS Clinical Research & STDs | ISSN: 2572-7370
- Journal Of Alcoholism Drug Abuse & Substance Dependence | ISSN: 2572-9594
- Journal Of Allergy Disorders & Therapy | ISSN: 2470-749X
- Journal Of Alternative Complementary & Integrative Medicine | ISSN: 2470-7562
- Journal Of Alzheimers & Neurodegenerative Diseases | ISSN: 2572-9608
- Journal Of Anesthesia & Clinical Care | ISSN: 2378-8879
- Journal Of Angiology & Vascular Surgery | ISSN: 2572-7397
- Journal Of Animal Research & Veterinary Science | ISSN: 2639-3751
- Journal Of Aquaculture & Fisheries | ISSN: 2576-5523
- Journal Of Atmospheric & Earth Sciences | ISSN: 2689-8780
- Journal Of Biotech Research & Biochemistry
- Journal Of Brain & Neuroscience Research
- Journal Of Cancer Biology & Treatment | ISSN: 2470-7546
- Journal Of Cardiology Study & Research | ISSN: 2640-768X
- Journal Of Cell Biology & Cell Metabolism | ISSN: 2381-1943
- Journal Of Clinical Dermatology & Therapy | ISSN: 2378-8771
- Journal Of Clinical Immunology & Immunotherapy | ISSN: 2378-8844
- Journal Of Clinical Studies & Medical Case Reports | ISSN: 2378-8801
- Journal Of Community Medicine & Public Health Care | ISSN: 2381-1978
- Journal Of Cytology & Tissue Biology | ISSN: 2378-9107
- Journal Of Dairy Research & Technology | ISSN: 2688-9315
- Journal Of Dentistry Oral Health & Cosmesis | ISSN: 2473-6783
- Journal Of Diabetes & Metabolic Disorders | ISSN: 2381-201X
- Journal Of Emergency Medicine Trauma & Surgical Care | ISSN: 2378-8798
- Journal Of Environmental Science Current Research | ISSN: 2643-5020
- Journal Of Food Science & Nutrition | ISSN: 2470-1076
- Journal Of Forensic Legal & Investigative Sciences | ISSN: 2473-733X
- Journal Of Gastroenterology & Hepatology Research | ISSN: 2574-2566
- Journal Of Genetics & Genomic Sciences | ISSN: 2574-2485
- Journal Of Gerontology & Geriatric Medicine | ISSN: 2381-8662
- Journal Of Hematology Blood Transfusion & Disorders | ISSN: 2572-2999
- Journal Of Hospice & Palliative Medical Care
- Journal Of Human Endocrinology | ISSN: 2572-9640
- Journal Of Infectious & Non Infectious Diseases | ISSN: 2381-8654
- Journal Of Internal Medicine & Primary Healthcare | ISSN: 2574-2493
- Journal Of Light & Laser Current Trends
- Journal Of Medicine Study & Research | ISSN: 2639-5657
- Journal Of Modern Chemical Sciences
- Journal Of Nanotechnology Nanomedicine & Nanobiotechnology | ISSN: 2381-2044
- Journal Of Neonatology & Clinical Pediatrics | ISSN: 2378-878X
- Journal Of Nephrology & Renal Therapy | ISSN: 2473-7313
- Journal Of Non Invasive Vascular Investigation | ISSN: 2572-7400
- Journal Of Nuclear Medicine Radiology & Radiation Therapy | ISSN: 2572-7419
- Journal Of Obesity & Weight Loss | ISSN: 2473-7372
- Journal Of Ophthalmology & Clinical Research | ISSN: 2378-8887
- Journal Of Orthopedic Research & Physiotherapy | ISSN: 2381-2052
- Journal Of Otolaryngology Head & Neck Surgery | ISSN: 2573-010X
- Journal Of Pathology Clinical & Medical Research
- Journal Of Pharmacology Pharmaceutics & Pharmacovigilance | ISSN: 2639-5649
- Journal Of Physical Medicine Rehabilitation & Disabilities | ISSN: 2381-8670
- Journal Of Plant Science Current Research | ISSN: 2639-3743
- Journal Of Practical & Professional Nursing | ISSN: 2639-5681
- Journal Of Protein Research & Bioinformatics
- Journal Of Psychiatry Depression & Anxiety | ISSN: 2573-0150
- Journal Of Pulmonary Medicine & Respiratory Research | ISSN: 2573-0177
- Journal Of Reproductive Medicine Gynaecology & Obstetrics | ISSN: 2574-2574
- Journal Of Stem Cells Research Development & Therapy | ISSN: 2381-2060
- Journal Of Surgery Current Trends & Innovations | ISSN: 2578-7284
- Journal Of Toxicology Current Research | ISSN: 2639-3735
- Journal Of Translational Science And Research
- Journal Of Vaccines Research & Vaccination | ISSN: 2573-0193
- Journal Of Virology & Antivirals
- Sports Medicine And Injury Care Journal | ISSN: 2689-8829
- Trends In Anatomy & Physiology | ISSN: 2640-7752

Submit Your Manuscript: <https://www.heraldopenaccess.us/submit-manuscript>